

ISic0621

I.Sicily inscription 0621

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Prag 2015-01-15

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 50115

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 16 cm

Width 24 cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 50 mm

Line 2: 30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]x · tr[---]

2. [---]vetus[---]

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644875

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 634 fig.51

Wilson, R.J.A. 1990. Sicily under the Roman Empire: the archaeology of a Roman

province, 36 B.C. - A.D. 535. Warminster. At 40 n.70

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